

Computational ethology (with a focus on social insects)

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Reviews in Quantitative Biology

Outline

- Motivation
- Automated tracking in social insects
 - Examples
 - Anatomy of a tracking system
- Challenges, outlook

Ethology

Niko Tinbergen
'Instinct'

Karl von Frisch
Honeybee waggle dance

Konrad Lorenz
Imprinting

1973 Nobel Prize
in Physiology and
Medicine

Methods:

Ethology

Manual scoring of behavior is still the dominant approach in the field

Downsides:

- Labor-intensive, slow, dull

A manual ant ethogram

One colony of *Pheidole* ants
 26 behaviors
 2331 behavioral acts recorded
 over 5 days

Ethology

Manual scoring of behavior is still the dominant approach in the field

Downsides:

- Labor-intensive, slow, dull
- Imprecise and subjective

Experimenter bias

THE EFFECT OF EXPERIMENTER BIAS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF THE ALBINO RAT

by Robert Rosenthal and Kermit L. Fode

Harvard University and University of North Dakota¹

Day	Asst.	Bright	Dull	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i> (one-tailed)
1	1.20	1.33	0.73	2.54	.03
2	3.00	1.60	1.10	1.02	NS
3	3.80	2.60	2.23	0.29	NS
4	3.40	2.83	1.83	2.28	.05
5	3.60	3.26	1.83	2.37	.03
Mean	3.00	2.32	1.54	4.01	.01

Ethology

Manual scoring of behavior is still the dominant approach in the field

Downsides:

- Labor-intensive, slow, dull
- Imprecise and subjective
- Low-dimensional

Ethology

Widely used methods to screen putative drugs

Significant controversy over interpretation and usefulness

(Fonio et al. 2012)

Low repeatability across drugs and labs (Carobrez et al. 2015)

Tail suspension test
Model of "depression"

Elevated plus maze
Model of "anxiety"

2500 published papers in 2005

Ethology

Manual scoring of behavior is still the dominant approach in the field

Downsides:

- Labor-intensive, slow, dull
- Imprecise and subjective
- Low-dimensional
- Limited by human vision and language

Computational Ethology

Automated acquisition and analysis of behavioral data

HARDWARE

SOFTWARE

Computational Ethology

Automated acquisition and analysis of behavioral data

Increase in throughput (genetic, pharmacological screens)

Unbiased

Increase in scope (e.g. discovery of behaviors missed by Humans)

An automated *Drosophila* ethogram

Supervised machine learning for behavior classification

Behavioral screen in *Drosophila*

“A gut microbial factor modulates locomotor behaviour in *Drosophila*”. Schretter et al., Nature (2018)

Behavioral screen in Drosophila

Caltech FlyTracker

about user guide download documentation acknowledge

FlyTracker aims to **track the pose** (position, orientation, size, wing- and leg positions) of **multiple flies** and **maintain their identities** throughout a video. In addition to trajectories, it outputs **features** (such as velocity, facing angle to other fly, and wing angles) useful for **behavior analysis**.

Gait analysis

Example: fish schooling behavior

“Hidden” interaction networks underlie behavioral contagion during collective evasion maneuvers

Rosenthal et al., PNAS (2015)

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Social insects

Integrated units of 10 – 1'000'000 individuals

Sophisticated division of labor and behavioral specialization

Complex communication, collective behavior

Social insects : challenges

Dense clusters, frequent and long-lasting visual occlusion
→ maintaining individual identity over time almost
always requires individual tags

Tracking social insects: example 1

QR codes on *Camponotus* ants

Scoring pairwise interactions

Social interaction network

Mersch et al., Science (2013)

Tracking social insects: example 2

Paint-marked *Ooceraea biroï* ants

Olfactory mutant shows impaired
social behavior:
Wandering phenotype
No trail following

Tracking social insects: example 3

28 cameras, 112 colonies
Paint-marked *Ooceraea biroï*

Individual specialization increases with
group size

Tracking social insects: example 5

Infrared camera (top)

Fluorescence camera (bottom)

QR labeled *Camponotus* ants

Fluorescently labeled food

Exchange of liquid food (trophallaxis)

Individual crop loads provide local control for collective food intake in ant colonies

Greenwald et al., eLife (2018)

Anatomy of a tracking system

The clonal ant *Ooceraea biroi*

No queens all workers reproduce (clonally)

- small colonies (≥ 10) are fully functional
- individual color tags (thorax abdomen)

Blind

- Tracking under visible white light

2mm long

1 webcam monitors 4-6 colonies

Simultaneous recording from 6 webcams w/ one computer

Up to 144 colonies can be monitored in parallel

5MP, color (RGB) images at 10 frames per second

Continuous ($\leq 48h$) or discontinuous (e.g. 10 min every 2h)

Anatomy of a tracking system

RBG image

Anatomy of a tracking system

Connected image regions “blobs”

- Size
- Centroid

Anatomy of a tracking system

Connected image regions: “blobs”

- Size
- Centroid

Anatomy of a tracking system

Anatomy of a tracking system

Anatomy of a tracking system

Color tag identification:

Create a training set of single ant blobs with well-defined thorax and abdomen tags

Train a (supervised) tag classifier

Classify candidate single-ant tracklets

ID-ed tracklets

Propagate ID's over tracklet network

Individual trajectories

$(x, y), t, ID$

Anatomy of a tracking system

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Going beyond (x, y) data

Fast animal pose estimation using deep neural networks

 Samuel S.-H. Wang, Mala Murthy, Joshua W. Shaevitz

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/331181>

Raw

Confidence Maps

Tracked

t = 0.00s

by Asaf Gal, the Rockefeller University (unpublished)

Behavior in the wild

Bird ringing

RFID: entry/exits from hive

GPS

ICARUS project

<http://www.orn.mpg.de/ICARUS>

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- Jaguar: <https://blog.londolozi.com/2013/09/14/the-jaguars-we-track/>
- RFID bees: <http://science.sciencemag.org/content/336/6079/348/F1>
- Bird ringing: <http://nc.audubon.org/news/how-banding-supports-bird-conservation-science>
- Basic tracking setup: <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0001083>
- Most social insects pictures: <https://www.alexanderwild.com/>